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on

**A Review Study on Customer Awareness and Perception Towards
Insurance In India - A Road Ahead for Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti
BeemaYojna for Financial Inclusion**

By

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Abstract:

Increasing rural income and improving infrastructure are expected to drive the growth of the Policies towards financial inclusion have received global attention including in the developed financial markets. There has always been concern about the excluded people who are out of the formal banking/financial system. Indian life insurance market. Factors such as better management of claims and regulatory trends, coupled with increasing income and the working-class population of the country are expected to drive the growth of the market. The study is indicated briefly to analyse the PMJJBY its impact to all the stakeholders and its competitiveness in the insurance Industry. Government of India is also highly concerned about the need of Insurance in current scenario and Launched *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana* for the benefit of general public. PMJJBY is a non-linked, non-participating,

one-year group term insurance product with renewability every year. This product has been designed by the insurance companies to meet the requirements of Government of India's "Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana" (PMJJBY) scheme. The study has been taken to review the relevant literature on financial inclusion and Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti beema yojana.

Key words: Customer Awareness, Customer Perception, Financial Inclusion, Insurance, Pradhanmantri Jivan Jyoti Bima Yojana, Scheme of Government

1. Introduction

Financial inclusion is the delivery of financial services at affordable costs to large sections of disadvantaged and low-income society (for example no frill account). In 2006, the RBI permitted commercial banks to make use of the services of NGOs/SHGs, microfinance institutions and other civil organizations as intermediaries for providing financial and banking services. According to the World Bank global financial inclusion survey (2012), only 35 percent of adults in the Nation had access to a bank account and only 8 per cent borrowed from institutional and formal sources. There are many activities of financial inclusion still pending. *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana* was introduced on 1st June 2015, under the promising *Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana* with the aim to provide financial support through cheaper term insurance to all the citizen of India with motto of "Jan-Dhan se Jan Surakhsha".

Product Highlights: -

Features	Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY)
Eligibility	18-50 years
Number of Policy	One Policy Per Person
When to Join the Scheme?	Any time
Sum Assured (Fixed)	Rs 2 lakhs
Premium	Rs. 330 per annum
Cover stops at age	At the age of 55 years
Maturity Benefit	Nil
Death Benefit (Natural Death	Rs 2 lakhs

Death Benefit (Accidental Death)	Rs 2 lakhs
Disability of both eyes, both hands, both legs or one eye and one limb	Nil
Disability of one eye or one limb	Nil
Maximum Insurance cover	Rs.2 lakhs
Risk Period	1st June to 31st May every year.
Mode of Payment	Premium will be auto debited from account in the month of May every

Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana is available Indian Residents between 18 and 70 years of age with bank accounts. It has an annual premium of ₹12 exclusive of taxes. The GST is exempted on *Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana*. The amount will be automatically debited from the account. The accident insurance scheme will have one-year cover from June 1 to May 31 and will be offered through banks and administered through public sector general insurance companies. In case of accidental death or full disability, the payment to the nominee will be ₹2 lakh and in case of partial Permanent disability ₹1 lakh. Full disability has been defined as loss of use in both eyes, hands or feet. Partial Permanent disability has been defined as loss of use in one eye, hand or foot. Further, death due to suicide, alcohol, drug abuse, etc. are not covered. This scheme will be linked to the bank accounts opened under the *Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana* scheme. Most of these accounts had zero balance initially. The government aims to reduce the number of such zero balance accounts by using this and related schemes. Now all Bank account holders can avail this facility through their net-banking service facility at any time of the year. Currently, Indian insurance companies such as LIC, ICICI Prudential Life Insurance, and SBI Life Insurance Company, among others, are introducing comprehensive custom-made micro-insurance products for the rural sector, which covers not just health but accidents as well.

STATE/UT-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF GROSS ENROLMENTS AND CLAIM AMOUNT DISBURSED UNDER PMJJBY AS ON 31.12.2018 (FROM : MINISTRY OF FINANCE)

Sl. No.	States/UTs	Enrolments	Amount Disbursed (In Crores)
1	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	15735	0.66
2	Andhra Pradesh	18278825	198.38

3	Arunachal Pradesh	38520	2.1
4	Assam	664860	62.22
5	Bihar	1442707	51.98
6	Chandigarh	54348	3.28
7	Chhattisgarh	1236185	100.88
8	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	22533	0.86
9	Daman & Diu	16204	0.52
10	Goa	120258	5.62
11	Gujarat	2429207	199.04
12	Haryana	895906	75.92
13	Himachal Pradesh	267267	17.24
14	Jammu & Kashmir	315534	2.74
15	Jharkhand	525273	28.6
16	Karnataka	3256551	217.6
17	Kerala	851753	23.68
18	Lakshadweep	1682	0
19	Madhya Pradesh	2008339	180.22
20	Maharashtra	3706638	211.2
21	Manipur	36680	2.58
22	Meghalaya	46266	2.18
23	Mizoram	56093	8.74
24	Nagaland	20669	1.48
25	Nct Of Delhi	923296	42.58
26	Odisha	1096845	75.98
27	Puducherry	69832	3.76
28	Punjab	678973	40.8
29	Rajasthan	1632800	146.5
30	Sikkim	28834	1.14
31	Tamil Nadu	2603089	126.04
32	Telangana	2065466	220.94
33	Tripura	117613	4.14
34	Uttar Pradesh	3642310	321.62
35	Uttarakhand	361626	28.1
36	West Bengal	1410931	79.12
37	Others	5849242	0
	Grand Total	56788890	2488.44

Interpretation: From above chart we can able to see that in India Andhra Pradesh is the state where largest number of gross enrolments in PMJJBY is made while Lakshadweep is the state where a smaller number of gross enrolments in PMJJBY. Gujarat is still behind with compare to other state in case of gross enrolment in PMJJBY.

Interpretation: From above chart we can able to see that in India Uttar Pradesh is the state where largest amount disbursed in PMJJBY while Lakshadweep is the state where a smaller amount is disbursed in PMJJBY.

PROGRESS OF PRADHAN MANTRI JEEVAN JYOT BIMA YOJANA:

Parameters	As on 01.11.2016	As on 01.12.2016	As on. 02.01.2017	As on. 01.02.2017
Gross enrolment reported by Banks subject to verification of eligibility, etc. (Amt. in Rs. Crores)	3.0652	3.0743	3.07949	3.0829
Total No. of claims recd.	46490	49477	51916	55371
Total No. of claims disbursed	42229	44644	48277	51601

Note: Data are based on information provided by Banks and Insurance companies to Jan Suraksha Mission Office (DFS)

Progress of the Scheme is as under (Cumulative):

Financial year	Total No. of persons Enrolled	Total No. of claims Received	Total No. of Claims Disbursed
2016-17	3.10 Crores	62,166	59,118
2017-18	5.33 Crores	98163	89,708
2018-19	5.92 Crores	1,45,763	1,35,212
2019-20(As on 06/12-2019)	6.43 Crores	1,74,274	1,59,574

Source: Jan Suraksha Website (06/12/2019)

Total No. of persons Enrolled(in Crores)

Interpretation: PMJJBY Scheme was started in year 2015. As you can check from above chart that in initial year 2016-17 total number of persons enrolled in this scheme is 3.10 crores while total 62,166 claims received. While in latest year 2019-20 total 6.43 crores persons enrolled in this scheme and total 1,74,274 claims received and from that 1,59,574 claims disbursed. It shows how efficiently this scheme is working.

Progress in 2019-20 (Cumulative):

	As on 6/12/2019	As on 29/11/2019	Addn(Redn) Over the Week	Addn(Redn) during the previous Week
Total No. of persons enrolled	6.4265 crores	6.4139 crores	1.26 lakh	0.33 lakh
Total No. of claims received	1,74,274	1,73,131	1,143	886
Total No. of claims disbursed	1,59,574	1,58,560	1014	1,408

Source:Jan Suraksha Website (06/12/2019)..

Interpretation:As you can check from above table that progress of PMJJBY Scheme in year 2019-20 that there are total 1,73,131 claims received till now and total 1,58,574 claims disbursed till the date 6/12/2019.

It is very essential that each and every citizen take part in the financial aspects of the country. It is essential to note that Financial Inclusion of the poor will help in bringing them to the mainstream of growth. This aspect of rural financial inclusion has seen a predominant fast

growth due to the *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana*. This is considered to be a greater leap in the financial development of the country. Hence this study has been undertaken to analysis Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Scheme and performance of this scheme in India

2. Objective of The Study

A number of studies have been conducted by various researchers regarding financial inclusion. Various types of schemes are launched by the government in order to extend the financial inclusion. Out of these schemes most recently our prime minister launched PMJJBY in 2015. Hence, many studies have not been available on this scheme. Various types of studies such as impact, implication, awareness and satisfaction level and attitude of beneficiaries regarding this scheme have also been conducted by various researchers. Keeping this aspect in mind the present study title, A review study on *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Beema Yojana*- A new scheme toward financial inclusion is being undertaken. Following are the objectives of this paper;

- To review customers' Perception and awareness Insurance and *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana*
- To review preference, attitude and satisfaction of beneficiaries towards insurance and *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana*

3. Research Methodology

Revisiting reviews cover under the category of Exploratory and this was Qualitative research design which was based on secondary data. In this present study an attempt has been made to explore the literature on financial inclusion and Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Beema Yojana. For this study selected research works have been collected and out of those collections only thirty-six literatures have been considered here, thus this research was based on Secondary data. For the purpose of this study 48 research papers have been studied. Out of these papers just 36 papers related to the scope of the study. These journals provide the admirable work of the various scholars worldwide which ultimately help the researcher to conduct their research conveniently. The research papers based on overview, current status and future vision of financial inclusion and state wise awareness level of respondents regarding the new scheme of financial inclusion PMJJBY.

4. Reviews of the Literature

In this section critical reviews have been given including Insurance in India from LIC to PMJJBY, so here how the development of insurance remains till date have been presented, which has been followed by customer perception, awareness, preference and ended with Financial Inclusion- Government schemes in India to study the objective of the study.

Life Insurance & General Insurance in India

Agarwala (1961) in his historical and analytical study entitled. 'The LIC in India' pointed out that in the developing countries, life insurance was an expanding phenomenon. Before the nationalization of the LIC, the life insurance market was narrow and highly imperfect, which was due to the under development of the country's national economy. But after nationalization, the LIC has made an excellent progress in the number of policies sold and the sum assured mobilized. Later Desai (1973) in his study entitled, 'Life Insurance in India – its history and Dimensions of growth' stated that the origin and development of the life insurance in India over the years has wide spread mindedness in insurance and the significant sales through service initiatives, executive efficiency, economy and promptness and spreading the benefits of life insurance to vast section of the rural population. The study of Satpal Singh (1986) on the title, 'Role of life Insurance in Economic Development of India' observed that the LIC had failed to compete with other saving media in tapping the household savings. He also found in his study that there was a vast scope for mobilization of savings of households through life insurance. He suggested that the life insurance protection should be extended to irregular income earners too. trial workers throughout the country could achieve a formidable growth in LIC. In this line Roy (1987) in his study on 'Life Insurance Lightens the Hope of the People', emphasized that the idea of insurance has gained momentum due to the growth and increasing uncertainties of human lives in the society and also reported that the Rural Career Agent scheme and Jana Raksha Policy for the rural masses had made steady progress in highlighting the idea of life insurance in rural areas. Moreover, Arora (1988), in her doctoral work, studied quantitative analysis of the investment policy of GIC and examined critically the role played by the GIC in providing finance to industry. The study revealed that the Investment Policy of GIC evolved within the ambit of the provisions of the Insurance Act 1938, and the guidelines issued by the government from time to time, with a view to maximizing investment income, ensuring safety, liquidity of funds and being consistent with national objectives and priorities under the guidelines. It also

invested in corporate securities and participated in underwriting of new issues. The promotional role played by the GIC over the years has been considerable. It has taken keen interest in the area of rural insurance, foreign business development and development of human resource.

Negi and Sarkar (1995), in their paper, analysed and critically examined the portfolio management policy of LIC with respect to its investment in Govt. of India's securities. The study revealed that up to 1987, the LIC had increased its investment under the Government of India's securities with the increase of its total controlled fund. But after 1987, its investments under the two heads did not increase with the increase in total controlled funds. After 1987, the corporation decided to take more risk in order to earn higher returns. It decided to be little aggressive for their portfolio management and tilted towards investment in securities and financial instruments where higher returns were possible, keeping in view the satisfaction of customers. It was important for the corporation to earn higher profit so that bonus might be declared at a higher rate. According to Jampala and Adilakshmi(2006), long term nature of business, stringent solvency margin norms, capon Foreign Direct Investment at 26%, cost overruns, low agent productivity coupled with high attrition, capital constraint and value conscious consumers were cited as few reasons for the under-performance of the private insurers in India. Authors also feel that consolidation in the sector is inevitable. By acquiring scale, managing expenses and being selective about the quality of business, new life insurance companies may be successful. Nanda (2007) has recorded the huge potential in the country in the life insurance market and states that India was the second fastest growing economy in the world next to China and the fourth largest economy in terms of purchasing power parity. Citing a NCAER report, the author observes that 30% of India's population has the earning capability between Rs.80000 and Rs.2 lakhs and adds that 50% of this population lives in the rural areas, which provides the huge opportunity for life The author describes the attitudes, approach and skill required to become a successful life insurance agent. The review made thus far includes research work on the life insurance industry, in India and abroad and also on distribution of life insurance products. Ghosh Amlan (2011) inferred the relationship between life insurance sector reforms in India and the growth of life business in the post reform period. It shows that the relationship between the insurance sector reforms and development of the life insurance sector in India was bi-directional. It was due to the huge

potentiality of the life insurance market. M.Selva Kumar and J Vimal Priyan (2012) concluded that LIC continues to dominate the insurance sector. Private sector insurance companies also tried to increase their market share. Life insurance has today become a mainstay of any market economy since it offers plenty of scope for garnering large sums of money for long periods of time. The study compared premium, policies and market shares of companies. Chaudhary (2012) explained that today India was one of the fastest growing economies of the world. The Insurance Industry contributes to the financial sector of an economy and also provides social security to the people of a country. The income earning capacity and increasing rate of literacy were the key factors of the growth of the Insurance industry. This sector provides for the long-term contractual savings and security. The investors in life insurance were looking for both good return and life risk coverage. Salunkhe and Ahirrao (2013) examined claim settlement ratio of LIC with other insurance companies in India. Study observed that there were cases of frauds in claim settlement that may happened but if the policyholder uses proper precautions, he will prevent himself from fraud. LIC of India provides better corporate services for settling the customers' claim. D-mat may improve transparency and efficiency of the claim settlement. Authors studied comparison of claim settlement ratio of LIC with other life insurance industry and survey of policyholders and opinion regarding claim settlement. Yadav and Mohania (2013) the study entitled claim settlement of life insurance policies in insurance services with special reference of Life Insurance Corporation of India. Authors have focused on management framework o-f LIC for the settlement; impacts of claim settlement on the sale of life insurance policies by LIC of India, claim settlement process followed by LIC of India, awareness towards claim settlement among customers and analyse quality of service provided by LIC of India for claim settlement.

Consumer Perception and Insurance

Blattberg&Wisniewsk, (1989) Like other retail methods, online channels have various promotional tools such as corporate logos, banners, pop-up messages, e-mail messages, and text based hyperlinks to web sites. These types of promotions have positively affected Internet buying. Further Jonsson Petur (1994) in his study “Social Influence and Individual Preferences: On Schumpeter’s Theory of Consumer Choice” states that Schumpeter’s theory of consumer choice also assumes that customers’ preferences and tastes were generally

deficient, and factors such as experience, learning, innovation, and social environment affect the formation of preferences. According to Kunz (1997) ease in using the Internet as a means of shopping positively impacted the consumer's online shopping behaviour. Product promotions attempt to influence the consumers' purchasing behaviour.

According to Mandal (2006), Insurance being a service with very high degree of intangibility, the role of intermediaries was very vital to the distribution of insurance products. Individual agents dominate Indian life insurance distribution. Study lists down the key attributes to become successful as a life insurance agent. Agent's role does not come to an end with the sale of policy but it marks a beginning of a relationship between the customer and the agent as life insurance contracts were long by nature. The focus of the research of LIMRA (2006) was on U.S. distribution systems and the relationships between insurance carriers and practitioners in local communities who sell or recommend a company's products and services. The research explores the economics behind meeting the constantly changing demands of distribution. In this line Keerthi, P. and Vijayalakshmi, R. (2009) "A Study on the Expectations and Perceptions of the Services in Private Life Insurance Companies" reveals that the policyholders' expectations were well met in the case of certain factors reacting to service quality. But in the case of other variables, there exists a significant gap which means that policyholders have experienced low levels of service as against their expectations. Sahu et al (2009); conducted a survey on 150 respondents to determine the attributes affecting buying behaviour of consumers, investment pattern in life insurance services and compare the differences in consumer perception of male and female consumers. In their study they found that there are 6 factors which affect buying behavior while purchasing life insurance policies namely consumer loyalty, service quality, ease of procedures, satisfaction level, company image and best hospitals without worrying about the financial company client relationship. There was no difference between the perception of male and female preferences. Deepika Upadhaya (2012) has discussed identifying the key success factors in the insurance industry, in terms of customer satisfaction so as to survive fierce competition and increased market share. The study was conducted on 206 respondents from four major cities. The study was exposed to promote a better theoretical understanding and recognition of the complexities to service quality offered by insurance companies. Further, the result of the study addressed that customers' satisfaction was based on the

performance of the insurance company and concluded that the main critical element was the interaction of sales people. Manuel (2013); he conducted the study to understand the Consumer Perception about life insurance policies in Kottayam City. For this study the researcher used exploratory research design. This research was restricted to the consumers of Kottayam city. The sample which was taken was of 50 respondents belonging to various age groups. The survey was conducted to find out the attributes which affect decision making of consumers of life insurance policies which were return on investment, company reputation, premium outflow, service quality and product quality. The majority of respondents belong to the age group of 19- 28 years, male consumers captured 74% of the market, dominant income group was 5001- 10000 and LIC had the major stake. A study by Parida& Acharya (2014) in Uttar Pradesh found that the most prominent reason cited by the uninsured persons was that the insurance products were too expensive and nearly 38%of the uninsured households cited this as a reason for not taking insurance. Similarly, as many as 23%of the households felt that insurance was not very important. Rajavardhan and Jahangir (2015); the sample has been taken from Nalgonda district with 120 respondents. In their article conducted a survey on rural markets of Telangana to find out socio demographic and economic variables that have impact on decision of consumer perception. They found that gender and marital status people residing in urban areas invest more in LIC. He even found that maximum people opted for yearly payment plans. Major portion of holders belong to the service sector and average middle-class people. Maximum people invested in LIC on the basis of brand name and invest more in money back policies.

Customer Awareness of Insurance

A study (by Reshmi, et al. (2007) conducted on a community cross-section basis in Mangalore found that 64%of the242 respondents were aware of health insurance. Of the total respondents, 45%came to know about it through the media. The mean agreeable amount to be paid as the premium was found to be Rs. 1804. Middle and low-income groups preferred Government instruments to private instruments. Goodenow and Painter-Eggers of LIMRA (2007) electronically surveyed more than 1,000members of a national consumer panel in the US market in order to gauge consumers' financial literacy and their own assessments of their financial preparedness for the future. All participants were at least 25 years of age with a minimum household income of \$75,000. Research shows that households with incomes at

this level or more were far more likely to rely on a financial advisor than those whose household incomes were less than \$75,000 per year. They were also more likely to be presented with a myriad of solutions by financial services organizations. Data has been weighted by gender, age, household income, level of education, and marital status. Other key findings were that people of all age groups regardless of their marital status were most worried about their ability to pay for hospital and medical coverage, their ability to maintain current lifestyle in retirement and being debt-free. Altaf Ahmad Dar (2010) had done a comparative study of promotional strategies adopted by public and private sector insurance companies in India. His primary objective was to know the promotional tool of private and public insurers and comparative analysis on the basis of customer's response with a sample size of 300. The study revealed a remarkable fact connected with customers' perception about promotional tool of both private and public sector companies and also about the most effective tool to promote insurance products/services and private sector companies must be truer and reliable first to win the hearts of the customers and adopt to push strategies to attract and catch the customer and public sector is more reliable but not so good and innovativeness. In one of the study by NCAER (2011) which conducted a survey of 30,200 households across 29 States and Union Territories to gauge awareness levels about various insurance tools across all socio-economic groups found that apart from macroeconomic issues, the insurance penetration in India is low due to a number of other factors, like low consumer preference, untapped rural markets, and constrained distribution channels. In urban areas, life insurance penetration is approximately 65% and is considerably lesser in the low-income unbanked urban areas. The life insurance penetration in the banked rural segment is estimated to be approximately 40% and negligible in the unbanked rural areas. A high share of the insured belonged to the regular salaried or self-employed category. On an average, the income and education levels of the insured were higher than those of the uninsured. Television was the primary source of awareness about insurance. Further, males accounted for a higher share of the insured than females. There was a lack of awareness about insurance concepts while certain misunderstandings also prevailed even among policyholders. According to feedback received in the survey, the problem has been exacerbated due to: (i) agents' inability to clearly explain the features of the products; (ii) lengthy documents that were not user-friendly; and (iii) the perception that agents were only

concerned with their commissions. Zhang, Jansen, and Chowdhury (2011) specified that businesses should have a brand presence on many different social media sites to increase their consumer audience. "Research has shown that exposure to electronic word of mouth (EWOM) messages can generate more interest in a product category than can exposure to information produced by marketers". Prakash (2012) observed that consumer awareness is the knowledge that a consumer should have about his/her legal rights and duties. It is must for a consumer to follow these rights. It is implemented for the protection of the consumer, so that the consumer is not exploited by the seller of the products. Consumer awareness is making the consumer aware of His/ Her rights. Dar (2013) carried out a community-based cross-sectional study towards the awareness of life insurance in the population of Jammu and Kashmir State. A total number of 242 respondents from 242 households were interviewed by using a pretested questionnaire after obtaining informed consent from the participants. The awareness of life insurance was found to be 64.0 per cent. Around 45.0 per cent of the respondents came to know about life insurance from the media which played an important role in the dissemination of information. The mean premium amount agreeable to be paid by the respondents for life insurance was found to be Rs.1804.00; even the low socio-economic group of people was also willing to part with a reasonable amount of Rs. 697.00 annually for life insurance. The middle and low socio-economic groups favoured government life insurance compared to private life insurance as they have more faith in Government Company. Thirumaran et. al (2015) has found that insurance companies in India were vital for one's saving purpose. He made a study to know the awareness level of customers about insurance products, factors influencing the selection of Insurance products. The study revealed that the beginning of Insurance was looked at as a 'tax-benefit' investment. Slowly, however the mindset of the common man is changing. Life Insurance is now looked on as an investment vehicle. With the introduction of private players in the sector there has been more transparency and flexibility in the sector. Better services, individual attention and pure transparency have given the private sector an upper hand

Customer Preference of Insurance

Alinvi and Babri (2007) the study was specifically conducted on young consumers from 18-27 years. In their article, they tried to find an answer to the question how could insurance companies enhance their ability of constant changes in customer preference in an

increasingly competitive environment. In this theory they found income flow, age, family size as significant determinants, information about product and services also affect consumer preference, options of products and services. i.e. customer choice along with time play an important role. Through this study it was concluded that price is a decisive factor for young customers of insurance services. We also concluded that there exists unawareness among young people about the services provided by insurance companies, as well as afraid of being fooled or tricked by telemarketers representing insurance companies. Thus, they demand more information. While the internet is their primary source of awareness but they prefer personal contacts too while making decisions. However, it was concluded that most respondents showed a tendency to change their preferences over their lifetime, as their life circumstances would change. Ahmed, et al (2007) the secondary study was conducted based on SERVQUAL MODEL in Bangladesh and found that people tend to invest more in private insurance companies due to better quality of services. Among private local and foreign insurance clients prefer foreign private insurance companies due to experiences in operation and wide area coverage, Companies must invest on building their reputation in order to reduce outflow of clients. They even found that 25% of respondents have chosen their insurance company with the influence of sales personnel. Yadav and Tiwari (2012) The study area is limited to Jabalpur District, of Madhya Pradesh and sample size of 150 policy holders is taken and the sample have been selected through a stratified and purposive sampling method. The study has been conducted to find out factors influencing customer investment decisions, impact of various demographic factors, preferences of customers while taking the decision, and ranking of factors responsible for the selection of life insurance as an investment option. The study was conducted on 150 respondents. In their study on factors affecting customer investment in life insurance policies and found that age, gender, income level. Out of 150 samples 54.6% of policy holders have invested in LIC followed by SBI life insurance amongst private players. The features that policyholders consider while making a purchase can be ranked as follows: company reputation, money back guarantee, risk coverage, low premium and easy access to agents as 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th respectively. Thus, it could be concluded that goodwill of the company is the most influencing factor while making policy buying decisions. It was found that the majority of respondents preferred money back policy. Venkaiah and Sudhir (2013); conducted a survey to find out the performance of

private insurance players and took a sample of 200 respondents. They found that very few respondents felt private companies were better than the public. The services offered by private companies were as per expectation of the customer and they feel no risk in investing in private companies. Respondents want more policies with tax benefits among private companies. Piyali Chandra Khan and Mitra D(2014) analyzed that the overall position of LIC was found to be quite satisfactory as the profit after tax improved by 270% in the last 12 years. It had a strong liquidity position. The company had sufficient current assets to meet the current liabilities. This resembles that LIC is quite capable to earn superior return in this competitive environment.

Financial Inclusion with Government Schemes In India

The study entitled, “PMJDY: A National Mission on Financial Inclusion in India”, by Gitte Madhukar, R (2012), focused on all the households in the country, with reference to access to bank accounts and other banking facilities. The study highlighted the need for financial inclusion, main features and pillars of the PMJDY and performance of this scheme. The poor and the underprivileged people in rural, semi-urban areas were expected to get all the benefits such as financial inclusion and financial freedom through the PMJDY. The study suggested comprehensive pilot studies to be conducted in each District to assess the borrowers’ perception, the actual requirement, the use of overdraft facility and on time payment and settlement. Hemant Kumar Watts., (2013), in his study entitled, “Implications of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana on Financial Inclusion and Inclusive Growth”, focused on the universal access to banking services, with at least one basic bank account for every household. The study concluded that creating a new account is not a challenge but increasing transactions is a great challenge. Sat Palwadhwa., (2015), in the research article on, “Financial Inclusion Plans and Its Performance Evaluation”, observed that success of financial inclusion plans is possible only when banks penetrate into villages, to cater to the financially excluded segment, with the purpose of providing banking services. The study concluded that the Government is trying to penetrate into six lakh villages to cater to the financially excluded segment, with the objective of providing banking services in unbanked and under banked areas.

Critical Evaluation of the Reviews

Current work aims to understand the expectation of customers and the impact and implementation of the Government of India insurance schemes with special reference to PMSBY and PMJJBY. The awareness of policyholders about their rights and duties are less with respect to life insurance contracts. The study found a low level of awareness across different demographic groups. The study revealed that the beginning of Insurance was looked at as a 'tax-benefit' investment. Slowly, however the mindset of the common man is changing. Life Insurance is now looked on as an investment vehicle. With the introduction of private players in the sector there has been more transparency and flexibility in the sector. Better services, individual attention and pure transparency have given the private sector an upper hand. It is very essential that each and every citizen take part in the financial aspects of the country. So, on the basis of studies it can be concluded that time to time various type of measures adopted by GOI and RBI in order to explore the financial inclusion and various awareness camps were also conducted by bank branches in various state to explore the knowledge regarding the new scheme of financial inclusion i.e PMJJBY. As no study found on RBI role it is suggested that the role of RBI and commercial banks should be included which may be included clients and plan a coordinated campaign in partnership with trainers to educate customers about the *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Beema* schemes of financial inclusion. The above studies indicate that there was a lack of sustained focus to expand coverage leading to a dip in enrolment. The scheme also suffers a number of operational issues, which are: (i) acknowledgment receipt for policy, (ii) limited understanding about the schemes among BMs/agents because of the limited capacity building by banks; (iii) no tracking mechanism for the agents and customers to follow enrolments, renewals, and claims. Moreover, no study found focusing on the role of Government banks, we suggest and believe study should be done on measures like expanding *Jan Suraksha* outreach in next 2-3 years through strong mass media campaigns by banks. They should also focus on the Government and banks have to take still more steps in reaching these schemes for all the people. Also, how The Government and banks have to maintain still more transparency in informing how the money collected from these schemes will be utilized by the Government/ bank. Study should be focused on how People from all the sectors have to come up voluntarily to uplift these schemes. From the above study it can be said that the beginning of providing social security benefits to a large number of unorganized people is

really good. The subscribers for these schemes are at increasing pace, however if implemented still more properly and the benefit is passed on to the real subscriber it will go a long way in establishing a social security system to the large section of society which has remained uncovered.

Conclusion: From above study it is analysed that the awareness of policyholders about their rights and duties are less with respect to life insurance contracts. The study found a low level of awareness across different demographic groups. The study revealed that the beginning of Insurance was looked at as a 'tax-benefit' investment. Slowly, however the mindset of the common man is changing. Life Insurance is now looked on as an investment vehicle. With the introduction of private players in the sector there has been more transparency and flexibility in the sector. Better services, individual attention and pure transparency have given the private sector an upper hand. It is very essential that each and every citizen take part in the financial aspects of the country. It is essential to note that Financial Inclusion of the poor will help in bringing them to the mainstream of growth. This aspect of rural financial inclusion has seen a predominant fast growth due to the *Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana*. This is considered to be a greater leap in the financial development of the country. So, on the basis of the above study we can say that the government should come out with a policy, where the public can be made to contribute to a life insurance scheme to ensure unnecessary events and also better utilization of life insurance facilities.

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